

1. DATA SUMMARY

DOI	Name of the dataset	Work Package (Task)
Principal type of data contained in the data set		
<input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative <input type="checkbox"/> Numeric <input type="checkbox"/> Text <input type="checkbox"/> Images <input type="checkbox"/> Audio <input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Databases <input type="checkbox"/> Non-structured data <input type="checkbox"/> Source code <input type="checkbox"/> Computational models <input type="checkbox"/> Time series <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):	
Data description		
Please, describe the data to be collected. Please specify the type and provide a short description of every field contained in the data. Moreover, add information about the size of the data set, format, etc.		
What is the source of the data?		
<input type="checkbox"/> Field work <input type="checkbox"/> Direct measurements <input type="checkbox"/> Surveys <input type="checkbox"/> Simulations	<input type="checkbox"/> Expert Knowledge, <input type="checkbox"/> Model Output <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):	
Methodology used to collect this data		
Please briefly describe the processes or methods which have been used to get the data.		
Relation to the data with the objectives of the project		
<input type="checkbox"/> Reduce the generation of RSU. <input type="checkbox"/> Increase the management of waste in favour of reusing and recycling. <input type="checkbox"/> Reduce the waste to landfill. <input type="checkbox"/> Reduce the management cost. <input type="checkbox"/> Reduce the generation of GHG emissions. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):		
Relation to the data with the results of the project		
<u>Operation and Planning:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Operation and Management Module. <input type="checkbox"/> Collection Module. <input type="checkbox"/> Planning Module. <input type="checkbox"/> Circular Economy Module. <u>APPs:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Food App. <input type="checkbox"/> Local Trade App. <input type="checkbox"/> Citizen App. <u>Educational Materials:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Innovative Teaching Units. <input type="checkbox"/> Sorting Game. <input type="checkbox"/> Eco-design Game. <input type="checkbox"/> Planning Game. <input type="checkbox"/> Virtual City Game.	<u>Citizen Science:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Eco-design solutions. <input type="checkbox"/> Planning solutions. <input type="checkbox"/> Circular economy solutions. <u>Prevention and Best Practices:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Economic instruments: New Pay-As-you-Throw (PAYT) schemes and incentives. <input type="checkbox"/> Innovative awareness actions including web-based tools for dissemination. <input type="checkbox"/> Best Practice Book. <u>New Treatments:</u> <input type="checkbox"/> Pre-dried and shredded bio-waste. <input type="checkbox"/> Bio-fuel and compost production plant.#	
Why is this data collected?		
Please, contextualize the information collected.		
Please, provide a brief description of any external dataset used		
For every external data set used please explain its origin, relevance and license.		

2. FAIR DATA (DATA FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSE)

2.1. DATA FINDABLE

Tim's 5-star classification of the dataset	
<input type="checkbox"/> Data is available under an open license <input type="checkbox"/> Use a structured data (e.g., Excel instead of image scan of a table) <input type="checkbox"/> Is available in a non-proprietary open format (e.g., CSV as well as of Excel) <input type="checkbox"/> Use URIs to denote things <input type="checkbox"/> The data is linked to other data to provide context	
Metadata standards	
Please cite the standard and format use for the data. If any this data set does not follow any standardized format, please provide a formal specification. For example, the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, Inspire Initiative, ISO, etc.	
Link regarding to metadata standard: http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/	
Documentation stored in the data	
<input type="checkbox"/> Information of the origin of the data <input type="checkbox"/> Codebook <input type="checkbox"/> List of abbreviations	<input type="checkbox"/> Description of variables <input type="checkbox"/> Technical information about files <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Ontologies	
<input type="checkbox"/> FIWARE Link regarding to fiware https://www.fiware.org/data-models	<input type="checkbox"/> Other external ontology Link regarding to ontologies https://www.w3.org/wiki/Lists_of_ontologies <input type="checkbox"/> Our defined ontology (please specify):
Whom might it be useful?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Public Administrations <input type="checkbox"/> Research groups <input type="checkbox"/> Citizens	<input type="checkbox"/> Private sector <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Channels to reach potential users	
<input type="checkbox"/> Personal/research group web page <input type="checkbox"/> Well-known specialist database <input type="checkbox"/> Search Administration database <input type="checkbox"/> Email of corresponding author	<input type="checkbox"/> Data access statement in published articles <input type="checkbox"/> Personal networking <input type="checkbox"/> Citation of data sets <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):

2.2. DATA ACCESSIBLE

Accessibility	
<input type="checkbox"/> Public data	<input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
Obligation or intention to publish/share data	
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
When will the data be published?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Immediately on collection <input type="checkbox"/> Within sometime after the ends of the project (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> Within sometime after its collection (please specify):	<input type="checkbox"/> To coincide with publication of main results <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Expected difficulties file sharing	
<input type="checkbox"/> Confidentiality <input type="checkbox"/> Large file size <input type="checkbox"/> Ownership/licensing	<input type="checkbox"/> Intended commercialisation <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):

2.3. DATA INTEROPERABLE

File format			
Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
Methods or software tools needed to access the data			
Please detail any necessary software to manipulate the information (if not standard).			

2.4. DATA REUSE

License conditions and restrictions	
<input type="checkbox"/> Copyright <input type="checkbox"/> Creative Commons (please specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Open Licence (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Please, list the owners of the copyright and intellectual property involved	
Access permissions and restrictions	
List roles/individuals (internal & external) with any limitations to access (e.g. scope, actions permitted), including who has authority to grant additional access.	

3. DATA MANAGEMENT AND ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Partners	Collection	Curation	Preservation
Foundation Deusto.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Zabala Innovation Consulting S.A.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Town hall of Zamudio	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Association of industries cluster environment Euskadi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Green Technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Enbio Epe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
National Technical University of Athens-NTUA	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
University of Patras	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dimos Chalandriou	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Serious Games Interactive APS	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ars Ambiente SRL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Comune di Seveso	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Legambiente Lombardia Onlus	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Softline SRL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Moba Mobile Automation AG	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EMAC Municipal enterprise environment Cascais	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?			

How will these be covered?	
Primary storage medium and location	
<input type="checkbox"/> University shared or research storage <input type="checkbox"/> Secure facility from a data provider <input type="checkbox"/> Physical storage <input type="checkbox"/> Cloud platforms (e.g. Github) <input type="checkbox"/> Last resort platforms (e.g. Zenodo)	<input type="checkbox"/> Academic research network platforms (e.g. ResearchGate). <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional open data repositories (e.g. CKAN based) <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Link regarding to data repositories: http://www.re3data.org/	
Data curation processes	
Please briefly describe the management of data throughout its life cycle.	
How will long-term preservation and access be assured?	
Please briefly describe how the data will be preserved after the end of the project.	
Regularity of backups and data performed. Replicas in other different places (if any)	
File management versioning	
<input type="checkbox"/> Unnecessary (i.e. overwrite original file) <input type="checkbox"/> Control version software (e.g. Git, please specify):	<input type="checkbox"/> Date/version number in filename/folder <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):

4. ETHICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS

Ethical aspect (If know)
<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (briefly describe): Aspects regarding informed consent in data collection and information protection in data storage and access. (Fulfilment of Ethical requirements are detailed in D9.1 – D9.7).
Legal aspect (If know)
<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (briefly describe):

5. OTHER ASPECTS

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